

THE CONSTITUENTS OF *DIDYMO-CARPUS PEDICELLATA*.
PART I. ISOLATION OF A NEW SERIES
OF COLOURING MATTERS.

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Didymo-carpus Pedicellata, N. O. *Gesneriaceae*, (Hindi, Pathar Phori : Sanskrit, Shila-Pushp ; Persian, Berg-i-Sang) is a small herbaceous plant found in the subtropical western Himalayan regions from Chamba to Kumaon at an altitude of 2,500-5,500 ft. The stem is nearly absent, sometimes upto $1\frac{1}{2}$ " long, and carries two or three pairs of opposite, glabrous, cauline leaves. The dry leaves have a characteristic spicy odour and appear dusted with reddish colouring matter. They are highly reputed in the indigenous medicine as a cure for kidney and bladder stones but the herb is not mentioned in Dymock's " *Pharmacographica Indica* " or Wehmer's " *Pflanzenstoffe* (Ed, 1930)." and no chemical investigation of it appears to have been so far undertaken.

As a result of the present investigation the following well-defined crystalline products have been isolated and characterised,

1. Pedicin, $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$: $C_{14}H_7 \cdot CO(OMe)_3 (OH)_2$, m. p. 145° , bright orange-red elongated rectangular plates (yield, 1.0%).
2. *iso*Pedicin, $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$, m.p. 105° , star-like aggregates of pale yellow prismatic rods and needles (yield, 0.4%).
3. Pedicinin, $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$: $C_{13}H_8O_4(OH)(OMe)$, m.p. 203° , carmine red aggregates of stout rods and needles (yield, 0.3%).
4. Pedicellin, $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$: $C_{15}H_7O(OMe)_5$, aggregates of colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 98° (yield, 1.0%).

The yields given above are the maximum noted in three samples worked and are based on the weight of air-dried, powdered leaves. *iso*Pedicin could be isolated from only one of these samples in which the yields of pedicin and pedicinin were considerably lower than the maximum (about 0.5 and 0.1% respectively). The yield of pedicellin did not appreciably vary in the different samples. Stocking the drug for a longer period was found to materially lower the yields of all the crystalline products. The molecular formulae, noted above, have been fixed on the basis of C, H, methoxyl and M. W. values. On the basis of C, H and M. W. estimations pedicellin could also be given the formula $C_{23}H_{24}O_7$ but its methoxyl value definitely points to the lower formula. Pedicin, on the other hand, gave abnormally low M. W. values by cryoscopic and ebullioscopic methods,

and also after Rast, but the C_{18} -formula for it was indicated by the values found for its single methoxyl group, and definitely established by the C, H and N values for its ammonium salt, $C_{18}H_{11}O_6, NH_4$, and the estimation of barium in its basic barium salt, $C_{18}H_{11}O_6, BaOH$.

The principal colouring matter, pedicin, which has been more fully investigated, was found to give a phenylhydrazone, showing the presence of a keto group in its molecule. It gave colouration with ferric chloride, was soluble in dilute caustic alkalies, insoluble in sodium carbonate and gave a water-insoluble lead salt. The presence of a phenolic hydroxyl in it is thus indicated. It also yielded a di-benzoyl derivative, whereby all the oxygen atoms in its molecule are accounted for as expressed in the formula noted for it above. It is unsaturated to bromine and could be reduced with Zn and HCl to a colourless hydro-derivative, whose analysis, however, indicates some other changes also, apart from the reduction of the double bond. In contrast to pedicin, pedicinin failed to give a phenylhydrazone, gave only a monoacetyl derivative and was soluble in dilute sodium carbonate solution. A discussion on the constitution of these products, which appear to be chalcone derivatives, will form part of a subsequent communication.

Apart from the products isolated and described in the present paper, an essential oil was also separated (yield, about 1.8%), which will be dealt with in a separate paper along with further constituents of the drug.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The drug was especially collected and supplied by the Himalayan Drug Company, Dehra Dun and kindly identified by Mr. C. E. Parkinson, the Botanist of the Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun, to whom the author feels deeply indebted.

After preliminary investigations for finding out the best method for extracting the various constituents of the drug, 4 kg. of the air-dried, glandular leaves were coarsely powdered and extracted with ether in a modified Soxhlet apparatus. The ethereal extract was concentrated to a small volume (about 1 litre) and allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature for several days, when a bright orange coloured crystalline powder (50 g.) forming the major portion of the colouring matter contained in the leaves, separated out; 18 g. of the crude colouring matter were further obtained on extraction of the ethereal mother liquors with dilute caustic soda solution, acidifying the alkaline solution with hydrochloric acid and cooling the ethereal extract of the acidic portion thus obtained. The

original ethereal layer, containing the neutral matter insoluble in caustic soda, was acidified with hydrochloric acid, washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate, concentrated to a small volume and kept in the cold, when a large quantity of a nearly colourless crystalline product (crude pedicellin) separated out, the mother liquors yielding a further quantity of it on treatment with petroleum ether. The highly odorous dark green residue, obtained on removing the solvent from the final filtrate from this product, was subjected to steam distillation. The non-volatile residue was extracted with ether and again separated into acidic and neutral fractions as stated above, when the neutral portion yielded through ether and petroleum ether mixture a further quantity of the crystalline neutral product (total yield, about 40 g.). The light greenish yellow product of steam distillation (yield 70 g. ; 1.8% on the wt. of the dry leaves) will be taken up, along with the constituents of the acidic mother liquors of the colouring matter and the mother liquors of crystalline neutral product, in a subsequent communication.

68 G. of the crude colouring matter were repeatedly extracted with ethyl acetate. Through alternate fractional crystallisation of the ethyl acetate soluble portion from benzene and ethyl acetate, 45 g. of pure pedicin (m.p. 145°) were finally obtained. The portion insoluble in ethyl acetate gave on repeated crystallisation from chloroform 11 g. of pedicinin (m.p. 203°) as a carmine-red, silky, crystalline product. No pedicine was obtained in this working. In a subsequent working of 500 g. of a fresh sample of the leaves, the mother liquor from pedicin gave 1.8 g. of isopedicin on repeated crystallisation of the fraction soluble in dilute ammonia (ca. 5%) from a mixture of ethyl acetate and ether, as a pale yellow crystalline product showing the end m.p. 105°. The crude neutral matter referred to above (40 g.) gave 30 g. of pedicellin on repeated crystallisation from ether, as a colourless, crystalline product finally melting at 96°.

Characterisation of the Constituents.

Pedicin ($C_{18}H_{18}O_6$).—Pedicin is fairly soluble in alcohol and chloroform, less so in ethyl acetate and benzene, sparingly soluble in ether and nearly insoluble in petroleum ether. It dissolves in dilute caustic soda and fairly concentrated ammonia to a deep brownish red solution with a violet colour but not in sodium carbonate, and gives an amorphous dirty red precipitate with lead acetate in alcoholic solution. Its alcoholic solution gives an evanescent greenish blue colouration with ferric chloride quickly changing to pale yellow which then slowly develops into deep red

and later reddish brown. It crystallises from organic solvents in bright orange-red, elongated, rectangular plates, m.p. 145°. It gives a reddish violet colouration with caustic soda and a deep red solution with concentrated sulphuric acid. [Found : C, 65.4 ; H, 5.3 ; OMe (after Zeisel), 27.2 ; M.W. (cryoscopic in phenol), 315 ; (after Rast), 328. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 65.5 ; H, 5.5 ; OMe (for 3 methoxyls), 28.1 per cent ; M.W. 330 ; $C_{21}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 65.1 ; H, 5.2 ; OMe (for 3 methoxyls), 24.2, (for 4 methoxyls), 32.2 per cent ; M.W., 384].

The Phenylhydrazone ($C_{18}H_{18}O_5$; $N \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_5$).—Pedicin (0.5 g.) was heated with phenylhydrazine (0.5 c.c.) on a water-bath and glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) added to the light red solution. After further heating for about 10 minutes in the course of which the colour deepened, water was added to the reaction mixture when a reddish pasty mass separated out which was well washed with water. On agitating it with a little hot alcohol a straw coloured silky, crystalline product resulted, which was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried (yield 0.3 g., 50% of theory). The phenylhydrazone, thus obtained, took on a greenish tinge on heating in solvents. It is very sparingly soluble in ether, fairly soluble in alcohol from which it crystallises in bundles of slender needles, m.p. 165-67°. (Found after drying at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 68.6 ; H, 5.8. $C_{24}H_{24}O_5N_2$ requires C, 68.6 ; H, 5.7 per cent).

The deep red filtrate from the phenylhydrazone gave a carmine-red, nitrogenous crystalline product, m.p. 190°, which will be described and discussed in a subsequent communication. The respective yields of the two crystalline products obtained through the action of phenylhydrazine on pedicine vary with the exact conditions employed, particularly with the duration of heating. The method given above was found to be most favourable for the regular phenylhydrazone (m.p. 165-67°).

Dibenzoylpedicin [$C_{18}H_{16}O_6 \cdot (C_6H_5CO)_2$].—Pedicin (0.3 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (5 c.c.) and benzoyl chloride (1.2 c.c.) was slowly added to the deep red solution with good cooling and stirring, whereby the colour lightened to pale orange and a white crystalline mass separated. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand for about an hour in the course of which the colour began to deepen, it was diluted with water and shaken up with a mixture of ethyl acetate and benzene. The light red benzene layer was well washed with water, dilute acetic acid and again with water, dried over sodium sulphate, filtered and concentrated, when pedicin benzoate crystallised out in colourless, short, scattered rods, which on recrystallisation from benzene melted at 181-83°. The mother liquors gave a further crop of crystals, m.p. 181°, (total yield 0.3 g., 60% of theory). It is sparingly

soluble in ether and petroleum ether, fairly soluble in alcohol, ethyl acetate and benzene and yields the original colouring matter and benzoic acid on warming with alcoholic caustic potash for 5-10 minutes on the water-bath. (Found after drying at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 71.1; H, 4.8. $C_{32}H_{26}O_8$ requires C, 71.4; H, 4.8 per cent).

Dibenzoylpedicin was also obtained through benzylation with caustic soda and benzoyl chloride, but the yields by this method were poorer and the isolation of the pure product more difficult.

Reduction of Pedicin.—A solution of pedicin (0.3 g.) in glacial acetic acid was shaken up in a small separating funnel with hydrochloric acid (10%, 1 c.c.) and ether (10 c.c.) with addition of small quantities of zinc dust till the original bright red colour had disappeared and a pale straw coloured ethereal solution was obtained. The ethereal layer was well washed with water and concentrated after drying, when the hydro product separated out as a straw coloured crystalline mass, which was fairly soluble in alcohol and ethyl acetate, less so in ether, sparingly soluble in petroleum ether, and on recrystallisation from ether melted at 211° . (Found after drying in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 64.6; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 64.5; H, 5.6. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 64.7; H, 4.5 per cent).

isoPedicin ($C_{18}H_{16}O_6$).—*isoPedicin* is readily soluble in alcohol and ethyl acetate, less so in ether, very sparingly in petroleum ether. It dissolves in dilute ammonia and is precipitated from the ammoniacal solution by hydrochloric acid. It crystallises from organic solvents in aggregates of pale yellow prismatic rods, m.p. 105° . It gives a deep red solution with concentrated sulphuric acid and on adding ferric chloride to its alcoholic solution it slowly develops a deep red colouration which later turns reddish brown. In contrast to pedicin it appeared to be saturated to bromine in the cold. (Found after drying at 50° in *vacuo*: C, 65.4; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5 per cent).

Pedicinin ($C_{18}H_{16}O_6$).—*Pedicinin* is fairly soluble in alcohol and chloroform in the hot, sparingly in benzene, nearly insoluble in ethyl acetate and ether, insoluble in petroleum ether and crystallises in aggregates of carmine-red, stout rods and needles, m.p. 203° . It dissolves in dilute caustic soda, ammonia and also in sodium carbonate forming orange-red to deep red solutions and gives an amorphous dirty red precipitate with lead acetate in alcoholic solution. Like pedicin and *isopedicin* it gives a deep red solution with concentrated sulphuric acid. On adding ferric chloride to its alcoholic solution it gives in contrast to them an *immediate* deep reddish brown colouration. [Found after drying at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 64.1; H, 4.1; OMe (after Zeisel), 10.3; M. W. (cryoscopic in phenol), 172,

(ebullioscopic in benzene), 150; (after Rast), 227. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.1; OMe (for 1 methoxyl), 10.3 per cent; M. W., 200).

The Ammonium salt ($C_{16}H_{11}O_6, NH_4$) was obtained on passing dry ammonia gas through a chloroform solution of pedicinin as a dark red powder in a quantitative yield. It is easily soluble in water forming a red solution and sparingly soluble in alcohol from which it crystallises in dark red stout rods, m.p. 149°, while the uncrystallised salt melts at 145°. (Found after drying at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 60.23; H, 5.38; N, 4.60. $C_{16}H_{13}O_6N$ requires C, 60.56; H, 4.73; N, 4.41 per cent).

The Barium salt ($C_{16}H_{11}O_6BaOH$) was obtained on adding an aqueous solution of barium hydroxide to an aqueous solution of the ammonium salt as a dark red semi-crystalline powder which was insoluble in the usual solvents and did not melt. (Found: Ba, 30.3, 30.7. $C_{16}H_{12}O_7$ Ba requires Ba, 30.3 per cent).

Monoacetyl pedicinin ($C_{16}H_{11}O_6OCCH_3$).—Pedicinin (0.2 g.) was heated on the water-bath with acetic anhydride (6 c.c.) and a crystal of fused sodium acetate added to the solution when a temporary darkening of colour occurred, which later on changed to orange-yellow. Water was then added to the reaction mixture. The yellowish oily layer, thereby obtained, later turned into a light yellow crystalline mass which, on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate, gave the acetyl derivative as light yellow, scattered, prismatic rods, m.p. 175°, in a nearly quantitative yield. (Found after drying at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 63.3; H, 4.2. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.1 per cent).

Pedicellin ($C_{20}H_{22}O_6$).—Pedicellin is fairly soluble in alcohol and ethyl acetate, sparingly soluble in ether, nearly insoluble in petroleum ether, and crystallises from all these solvents in aggregates of rectangular plates, m.p. 98°. It is insoluble in alkali and gives a deep red colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. [Found after drying at 50° in *vacuo*: C, 67.2; H, 6.3; M.W. (after Rast), 312, (cryoscopic in phenol) 469; Me (after Zeisel's method), 43.0. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 67.0; H, 6.1; M.W. 358; OMe (for 5 OMe), 43.0 per cent. $C_{23}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 67.0; H, 6.2; M.W., 421; OMe (for 5 methoxyls), 37.6; (for 6 methoxyls), 45.1 per cent). It does not form an acetyl or a benzoyl derivative by the usual methods and apparently does not contain a hydroxyl group in its molecule.